

LCR civic data and public service innovation Retrospective

Summary

On 17th February 2025, representatives across the Liverpool City Region collaborated in a retrospective exercise to bring together learnings from different, data-driven pilot projects to support insight for future Office for Public Service Innovation (OPSI) prototypes. The methodology of a retrospective allowed for discussions about what worked well, what challenges were uncovered, and what could be done to support prototype delivery in the future.

This report covers the details of the findings with key benefits of the work identified as:

- **Collaboration and knowledge sharing:** We recognised the value of bringing together experts from different sectors to share insights and best practices.
- **Identification of key themes:** The session highlighted recurring challenges and areas for improvement, such as data accessibility and governance.
- **Case studies and user cases:** Our collective data-sharing initiatives have demonstrated impact. These examples help build momentum for further work.
- **Best practices for developing a framework:** We recognised the need to a model for streamlining processes and developing a data repository.

There are several recommendations for future prototype project planning from the discussion, but there are **two key actions** that are foundational to future success and could be developed as soon as possible.

1. All projects identified challenges of setting up **frameworks for data sharing**, establishing the necessary trust and processes with an accepted legal basis. Having a unified **information governance framework** approved by all civic organisations in the region with clear processes for approvals would reduce the risk of projects getting “stuck” without any data.
2. There is a need for **access to training and a community of practice** around the use of data and digital, and innovation practices, to educate and enable individuals and teams to feel empowered to act.

Overall, the retrospective process helped to bring together projects that have been working to identify how to best use the data we have and to look at how innovative services could be developed. In summary the process outcomes were:

- Collaborative discussions helped surface key issues and priorities.
- Participants recognised the **value of shared learning and best practices**.
- Awareness of **cultural and organisational barriers** is a positive step towards overcoming them.
- There is consensus on the need for a **more strategic and phased approach to data sharing**.

Across all projects, what worked well?

1. Bringing the right people together:
 - Participants agreed that bringing together individuals from different organisations (local authorities, NHS, voluntary sector, analysts, policy teams) has been valuable.
 - The discussion itself helped identify common themes, challenges, and areas for collaboration.
 - Open and interactive discussions—such as clustering ideas on a shared board—helped to clarify thinking and priorities.
 - Joined up working and understanding across sectors; Working with partners with significant contact with residents demonstrated both the impact and appetite for private and third sector colleagues to participate and hold part of social solutions.
2. Recognising and prioritising key issues:
 - The session surfaced recurring data challenges, such as:
 - The difficulty of accessing and linking data across different organisations.
 - The complexity of information governance (IG) processes.
 - The lack of common identifiers across systems.
 - There was broad agreement on the importance of prioritising foundational issues, such as IG and data accessibility, before tackling larger-scale innovations.
 - Start with the desired outcome and work through the challenges.
3. Sharing learning and best practice:
 - The discussion acknowledged that many organisations are facing similar issues, and there are already good examples of how some challenges have been overcome.
 - There was consensus on the value of documenting and sharing best practices (e.g., how other cities have handled IG, successful data-sharing models, or lessons from past projects).
4. Awareness of cultural and organisational barriers:
 - The session highlighted wider cultural challenges, such as:
 - Fear of data sharing due to legal and compliance concerns.
 - Siloed working within and across organisations, making it difficult to collaborate.
 - Capacity issues, where analysts and data professionals are overloaded with routine reporting rather than innovative projects.
 - Recognising these barriers is a key step towards addressing them.
5. Consensus on a more strategic approach:
 - There was agreement that data-driven projects need clearer governance and prioritisation.
 - The group recognised the need to focus on projects with tangible impact, rather than trying to solve all problems at once.
 - There was an appetite for identifying "first-order" priorities (e.g., simplifying IG processes) before moving to second-order priorities (e.g., large-scale data integration).

Across all projects, what were the challenges?

1. Data accessibility and ownership:
 - Lack of understanding about data are available, and processes to obtain access, data controllers etc.
 - Lack of shared digital infrastructure
2. Information Governance (IG) barriers:
 - Lengthy bureaucratic IG and DSAs processes slow down projects
 - Lack of a common unique identifier across systems (e.g., NHS numbers not embedded in council records)
 - GP data-sharing agreements are particularly difficult to navigate (GP Practice autonomy: Decision-making and agreements to share data inconsistent between practices; Overcoming communication, and security concerns is time consuming: Engagement with GPs around data sharing often requires sustained effort and time to build trust and clarify responsibilities)
 - Lack of effective mechanism for following up on progress of DSA sign ups
 - Conditions for successful innovation (collective systemic action and the need for data, evidence, and insights availability) not consistently in place
3. Skills and capacity:
 - Lack of appropriate digital/data skills within public & 3rd sector organisations
 - There is too much reliance on individuals with specialist knowledge and needs to be more distribution of knowledge or mechanisms to exchange knowledge.
 - Lack of understanding about the importance of data
 - Many analysts are focused on statutory reporting rather than data innovation
 - Over-reliance on Excel instead of data tools and software.
 - Recruitment struggles, particularly in attracting younger talent.
 - Activities being seen as 'additional' to the day job
 - Allowing time to stop and reflect, to enable more structured planning and execution
4. Trust and ethical considerations:
 - Data-sharing initiatives require strong justification and transparency to gain public support.
 - Local resident buy-in required for success
5. Funding:
 - that Hard to demonstrate ROI from data-sharing initiatives to justify pump-priming finance and support for scaling innovations.

Across all projects, what are the opportunities?

1. Streamlining IG processes:
 - Adopting a regional IG framework could simplify data-sharing agreements and reduce project delays.
 - The OPSI SEG prototyping approach could be used to test and refine streamlined IG processes before full-scale implementation.
2. Analyst upskilling and training:
 - Expanding training programs can support transition from routine reporting to advanced data analysis.
 - Make use of the data science Analyst Training programme available through the Data Action Accelerator.
 - Pilot automation tools and upskilling programs, helping analysts transition from routine reporting to strategic analysis.
3. Establishing a Community of Practice:
 - Communicate activities, opportunities to learn and collaborate.
 - A network of data professionals across public sector organisations could facilitate knowledge exchange and innovation.
 - Share learning more broadly and hold centrally; develop expert client; require future programmes to reflect on these lessons before they start.
4. A central repository to enable sharing between organisations to include:
 - Methodologies
 - Processes
 - Systems
 - Data
 - Contacts
5. Pilot projects:
 - Selecting a high-impact issue (e.g., air quality and asthma-related hospital admissions) could demonstrate the value of data-driven interventions.
 - Building and demonstrating tangible links between data
6. Analysis of best practice:
 - Learning from LOTI to develop a roadmap for improving IG and data sharing.
 - LCR data sharing agreement to be tailored for different uses. e.g., work that LOTI have done across London LAs.
7. Cross-sector collaboration:
 - Deepen understanding of third sector organisations we work with, and their challenges.
 - In-person workshopping solutions with a wide variety of stakeholders across public, private and third sectors.

Recommendations

The LCRCA are best placed to drive to following recommendations (OPSI to convene)

Enhancing civic data and public service innovation

1. Prioritise Information Governance (IG) strategy:
 - Explore a regional IG framework to speed up approvals.
 - Identify quick wins, such as pre-approved data-sharing agreements.
 - Adopt the OPSI SEG Prototyping Approach and Framework to test and refine IG solutions.
 - Adopt a “learning lab” approach to provide a space to document and refine best practices for IG and data integration.
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2. Enhance data accessibility:
 - Develop a centralised data catalogue to help stakeholders understand available datasets.
 - Improve visibility of existing best practices and successful case studies.
3. Upskill analysts:
 - Expand analyst training programs to focus on modern data tools.
 - Encourage automation of routine reporting to free up analytical capacity.
4. Focus on high-impact pilot projects:
 - Select a specific use case (e.g., linking health and housing data for asthma prevention).
 - Use pilot projects to demonstrate return on investment and build public trust.
 - Adopt the OPSI SEG Prototyping Approach and Framework to pilot multi-agency data-sharing projects, embed a structured prototyping process and learning cycles

to ensure recommendations are tested within existing local structures before full implementation.

5. Strengthen cross-sector collaboration:
 - Formalise a public sector data network to support ongoing discussions and initiatives.
 - Encourage joint projects between councils, NHS, and other stakeholders.
6. Develop shared principles for data sharing
 - Develop guidelines for ethical and effective data-sharing across LCR using the OPSI SEG Prototyping Approach and Framework.

Aims and outcomes

	Aim of the retrospective	Themes/outcomes
A1	Identify/understand factors that have helped or inhibited projects/programmes	<p>Barriers to data sharing:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The discussion highlighted significant IG (Information Governance) challenges, particularly around data-sharing agreements. • The lack of common unique identifiers across different systems (e.g., NHS numbers not used in council databases) was identified as a major issue. • Bureaucracy and lengthy approval processes slow down innovation, with some projects taking months to resolve IG issues. <p>Positive examples:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The Safe and Well fire service initiative was recognised as a good practice in cross-sector data sharing, showing how trusted public sector professionals can support health and social care interventions. <p>Skills and capacity challenges:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Many analysts are overburdened with routine statutory reporting, limiting their ability to engage in innovative data projects. • Concerns were raised that the public sector struggles to attract and retain young data professionals, leading to an ageing workforce and slow adoption of modern tools. • There was recognition that too much reliance on Excel limits analytical capacity and that upskilling and new technologies is needed.

	Aim of the retrospective	Themes/outcomes
A2	Encourage targeted and structured collaboration	<p>Cross-Sector representation:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> The retrospective brought together local government, NHS, voluntary sector, data analysts, and policy professionals, creating a shared space for discussion. There was broad agreement that multi-agency collaboration is necessary to overcome data-sharing barriers. <p>Need for a data community:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Participants discussed the creation of a formalised data-sharing network to ensure continuous knowledge exchange. The importance of shared learning and case studies was emphasised to help teams avoid repeating past mistakes. <p>Areas for collaboration:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> A regional approach to IG reform was seen as a priority, with potential to develop standardised agreements and pre-approved data-sharing frameworks. Targeted projects, such as linking air quality and health data to improve asthma outcomes, were suggested as proof-of-concept cases to demonstrate the value of collaboration.
A3	Identify areas for improvement	<p>Governance and IG reform required:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> The IG process is slow, complex, and inconsistent across organisations. There was discussion about developing a regional IG framework, inspired by LOTI, to simplify approvals. <p>Investment in upskilling and technology:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Analysts need upskilling in modern tools beyond Excel. Data professionals need to be freed from low-value reporting tasks so they can focus on strategic analysis. <p>More work to be done to build trust:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Many people, including professionals within the system, are hesitant to share data due to perceived legal and ethical risks. Clear case studies showing how data sharing benefits citizens (e.g., reducing GP visits by linking social care and health data) could help change this perception.

Objectives and outcomes

	Objective of the retrospective	Themes/outcomes
O1	Understand the Region's capacity to deliver and generate recommendations that are anchored in existing infrastructure	LCR has strong expertise and motivation, but is constrained by governance, capacity, and structural barriers. Recommendations that emerged include: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Developing a city-region-wide IG framework to reduce approval times. • Training and upskilling analysts to improve data capabilities. • Automating routine reporting to free up analytical resources. • Expanding collaboration across councils, NHS, and voluntary sectors.
O2	Develop a user case that can be applied to different reports, including recommendations for the Office for Public Service Innovation and the Social Care Mission (i.e., the region's intelligence skills assessment and IG strategy)	The meeting helped define practical use cases for data-sharing improvements , such as: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Safe and Well fire service initiative – Using frontline workers for cross-service data collection. • Air Quality & Asthma Pilot – Linking environmental, housing, and health data to create targeted interventions. • Regional IG Framework Proposal – Using the LOTI model as an example for the Office for Public Service Innovation and Social Care Mission. <p>These examples can be incorporated into policy reports as evidence-based recommendations.</p>
O3	Establish a 'value proposition' that informs innovation and partnerships	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The group recognised the importance of framing data sharing as an enabler for better services rather than a compliance burden. • There was agreement that successful pilots must demonstrate return on investment (ROI) to gain wider buy-in. • A clearer public narrative on the benefits of data sharing is needed to build trust and reduce resistance from professionals and the public.
O4	Co-ordinate a set of principles (alongside Public Digital and the CDC-led Residents Assembly) that set out rules of engagement when sharing data	Core principles for future data projects were discussed and are summarised below. These should be co-ordinated with other principles in development. <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Transparency – Clearly communicate the purpose of data sharing. • Trust – Build public confidence through tangible success stories. • Efficiency – Streamline IG processes and eliminate unnecessary bureaucracy. • Collaboration – Strengthen networks across sectors. • Innovation – Move beyond compliance-driven reporting to proactive, data-driven decision-making. <p>The retrospective also supported exploring new approaches to data sharing, such as regional agreements, automation, and integrated digital platforms.</p>

Attendees

Name	Organisation	Project
Sara Chattun	Capacity	What's your Problem & Greater Data
Jacob Baisley		North Liverpool Prototype
Rob Tabb	CA	OPSI
Richard Jones	LCC	
Denise Bowman	BABS	
Carmel Doyle	BABS	
David Robinson		Safe & Well
Gavin Becket		
Gary Leeming	CDC	What's your Problem & Greater Data
Ellie Fielding	CDC	What's your Problem & Greater Data
Emma Lo	CHIL	Safe & Well
Seonaid Lafferty	Data Action Accelerator	

Projects involved and how these are linked to the discussion

- [What's your problem?](#)
- [Greater Data:](#)
- Children's safeguarding
- North Liverpool prototype
- The LCC Adult Social Care: Forecasting our composite predictive model worked so well and will have a practical impact on budget setting
- [Safe & Well Pilot project:](#) Development of dashboards sharing UPRNs for risk stratification of Safe & Well visits; Support in theory from GP practices
- [BABS Services:](#) Across five Boroughs to support the most at risk/vulnerable parents and babies often at risk of separation/removal